

Pyridine Compounds of Pentavalent Rhenium

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In a previous communication¹ an improved rapid method for the preparation of dioxotetrapyridine-rhenium (v) chloride, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$, and some of its properties have been reported. The preparation of some derivatives of the compound and their properties are described in the present communication.

The orange-yellow cyanido and the perchlorate of the cation $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ have been prepared by metathesis of an aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ with excess of KCN and NaClO_4 solution respectively.

The perchlorate is sparingly soluble and the cyanide is moderately soluble in water. Like the chloride, these are soluble in ethanol and acetone. The perchlorate has been found to be diamagnetic.

All these compounds are thermally unstable, liberating pyridine on heating, their stability diminishing in the order: $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{CN}^-$. Thus a sample of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{ClO}_4$ appears to be perfectly stable at the room temperature, but samples of the analogous cyanide lose pyridine slowly even at the room temperature. On heating samples of the chloride and cyanide at 50° , beautiful green and brown masses, respectively, are obtained. Investigation on the nature of these products and thermogravimetric analysis are being pursued.

An aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{Cl}$ of concentration $1.7 \times 10^{-3}M$, adjusted to an ionic strength of 0.2 with KCl, is reversibly reduced at a dropping mercury cathode. The polarogram indicates one electron change with $E_{1/2}$ value of -1.00 volt vs. S.C.E. at 28° . The $E_{1/2}$ is shifted towards more negative values in presence of increasing amounts of pyridine.

On addition of an excess of dimethyl sulphate to a saturated aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]\text{CN}$, an immediate brown precipitate is obtained. This is filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol, and acetone, and dried in vacuum. Analysis of the substance corresponds to the formula $\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})$. [Found: Re, 46.7; N, 10.2. $\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_2(\text{CN})$ requires Re, 46.3; N 10.4%]. The substance is insoluble in alcohols, acetone, benzene, chloroform, etc. but soluble in cold H_2SO_4 (conc.), forming an intense pink-coloured solution from which the original substance is recovered unchanged on dilution with ice-cold water. This also dissolves in excess of hot KCN solution which on slow evaporation over H_2SO_4 (conc.) gives rise to large orange crystals of $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$.

1. This *Journal*, 1963, 40, 81.

The same substance, $\text{ReO}_2\text{Py}_2(\text{CN})$, is also precipitated by keeping an aqueous solution of $[\text{ReO}_2\text{Py}_4]\text{CN}$ with methyl iodide in a sealed tube with occasional shaking. The substance is purified by precipitation from its sulphuric acid solution with ice-cold water. (Found: Re, 47.2; N, 10.5%).

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